

Abstract

There are many opportunities for the Canadian military to increase spending toward NATO targets. For example, direct and complete funding for the manufacturing of armaments in Canada with wholly owned military operations. Another example is UN Peacekeeping. This article describes how military spending could increase secondary goals, like global mining standards or domestic economic multipliers. The current amount of military spending is \$40 billion, and it must increase by \$20 billion to reach the NATO targets. This article presents a description of the cobalt mining industry in DR Congo. It estimates that it costs roughly \$20 billion for the Canadian government to produce as much cobalt each year using the military at domestic Canadian mines. The article also describes the Canadian GDP multiplier for such an amount of metal production. And the article describes potential ways to use the military to do infrastructure spending, either in foreign locations to achieve global aid goals or in domestic Canadian locations to achieve economic multipliers or national security goals.

Keywords: GDP, Military, NATO, Cobalt, DR Congo, Canada, Ukraine, Simulation, History, Statistics

JEL Codes:

B5 - Current Heterodox Approaches
C8 - Data Collection and Data Estimation Methodology Computer Programs
C81 - Methodology for Collecting, Estimating, and Organizing Microeconomic Data; Data Access
E6 - Policy Objectives ; Policy Designs and Consistency ; Policy Coordination
G1 - General Financial Markets
G17 - Financial Forecasting and Simulation
H2 - Taxation, Subsidies, and Revenue
H5 - National Government Expenditures and Related Policies
H57 - Procurement
K2 - Regulation and Business Law
K23 - Regulated Industries and Administrative Law
L5 - Regulation and Industrial Policy
L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products and Construction
L72 - Mining, Extraction, and Refining: Other Nonrenewable Resources
N5 - Agriculture, Natural Resources, Environment, and Extractive Industries
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Q4 - Energy
Q5 - Environmental Economics
Q32 - Exhaustible Resources and Economic Development
Q33 - Resource Booms
Y1 - Data: Tables and Charts

Canadian Military spending through UN Peacekeeping and more

This article discusses a methodology for modelling military spending. For example, Canadian government spending on UN Peacekeeping counts toward the NATO target for total military spending relative to GDP. This example reflects opportunities for new forms of “military spending”. The Department of National Defence may not be responsible for the spending, as NATO involves many other parts of the Canadian federal government. These other types of spending can be designed to impact the Canadian economy in new ways. For example, military spending can be targeted to achieve a domestic economic multiplier effect by fully funding domestic manufacturing of military armaments using only Canadian materials.

The total budget in 2025 for UN Peacekeeping is approximately \$10 billion USD, or approximately \$14 billion CAD. Canada accounts for approximately 2% of the total contribution of approximately \$300 million CAD (Fetterly, 2006; United Nations, 2017). That is only 1% of Canada's total military spending. UN Peacekeeping represents a potential area for new budgetary spending.

Total military spending in Canada was approximately \$40 billion CAD in 2024. Moreover, it must increase by \$20 billion to meet NATO targets. Canada's 2024 GDP was \$2.2 trillion USD or \$2.9 trillion CAD. Military spending accounted for approximately 1.3% of GDP, and it is estimated to reach 1.7% by 2030 (Government of Canada, 2025). How can Canada increase its military spending by \$20 billion more quickly? Are there ways to allocate this spending that also achieve other objectives? The broad definitions of the NATO targets provide new ways to design military spending that can achieve new goals. For example, military spending causes a local economic multiplier. Another example is military spending designed to achieve foreign aid goals, as further described below.

One way to increase military spending and GDP overall is to increase military spending through investments in domestic supply chains. If the military pays Canadian businesses to meet

military needs, then it can create new domestic sources of materials. For example, the military can operate as a sole operator or as a partner in a joint venture for domestic industries such as farming.

If the military begins operating farms in Canada, it may have a positive effect on local farmers by increasing overall production. The military may further invest in processing capacity in ways that further benefit local farmers. Alternatively, military spending may cause an adverse crowding-out effect in some cases. This crowding-out may be unintentional, and the impacts of each type of spending program require detailed analysis beyond this paper.

The Canadian government could use military spending to partner with Canadian farmers and food processors to develop specialized food products. Military rations present opportunities for innovation in food science. The Canadian military can fund a new domestic industry to meet its own needs and, potentially, supply the military of other countries around the world. These compounding economic impacts can achieve multiplier effects on Canadian GDP as new government spending increases overall.

In addition to farming and food, other relevant industries for the Canadian military include mining, energy, technology, and more. These are priority areas in which the Canadian government can increase military spending, with second-order effects. For example, if the Canadian military increases armament production in Canada at any price, using materials that are only produced domestically. In this case, the profit motive is not the primary concern of the businesses. The business is focused on the security of supply above all else. The scale of this subsidized production depends on the amount of government funding available and the costs of production.

The broad way that military spending is defined may include things like mining critical minerals in Canada. For example, the military could have a mandate to produce a matching amount of cobalt as the DR Congo does each year. The Canadian government could decide that it wants to use the military to support mining in Canada in a way that is meant to displace the

production from DR Congo because of concerns about human rights standards for mining there. That would be an unusual policy, but it provides valid numbers for comparison as detailed below.

Currently, mining in the DR Congo accounts for approximately \$10 billion in GDP, of which 80% is from cobalt. The amount of metal production is over 200,000 tonnes of cobalt per year—\$ 50,000 USD. The total cost of 200,000 tonnes of cobalt at current prices is \$10 billion USD or \$14 billion CAD (Statista, 2025). Could the Canadian military fund produce 200,000 tonnes of cobalt a year from Canadian sources? If it decided to do it at any cost, then what cost?

Considering that the gross metal value of all the cobalt from DR Congo is approximately \$14 billion CAD, the cost of production for that much metal within Canada by the military could be higher or lower. The cost of production could be \$20 billion or more if the military operated the mines at a loss. The cost of production could be \$10 billion or less if the military operated the mines at a profit. The government may not consider profit or loss as the primary concern for the operation, but rather focus on other goals like security of supply or global human rights standards.

As a unit of comparison, the Canadian government plans to increase military spending by \$20 billion CAD to meet NATO targets and this same amount \$20 billion, could approximately fund the cost of mining 200,000 tonnes of cobalt in Canada each year. This amount of mining activity has additional GDP multiplier effects within Canada (Natural Resources Canada, 2025).

If the Canadian government decides to use the military to subsidize domestic production, it will have several impacts. For one, the military spending will count towards GDP. For another, the mineral production will have a multiplier effect on GDP (Natural Resources Canada, 2025). The multiplier is calculated as the ratio between GDP impact and the value of mineral production. The value ranges from 1.75x for the direct GDP impact of mining, divided by the value of minerals production, up to 2.4x for the total direct and indirect GDP impact of mining on mineral value (Natural Resources Canada, 2025).

In this case, 200,000 tonnes of cobalt at \$50,000 USD per tonne yields a gross metal value of \$10 billion. The impact on total GDP in Canada ranges from \$17.5 -24 billion USD, which is \$24 - 33 billion CAD, and the direct and total GDP in Canada from the cobalt mining. This amount of GDP is combined with the \$20 billion in military spending that was initially used to fund the metal production. The total GDP impact ranges from \$44- \$54 billion from this new type of military spending.

It would be highly unusual for Canada to fund the build-out of a new industry domestically to crowd out a foreign source of production. This could be illegal, impractical, or immoral. However, it may be useful as a policy tool to reduce industry consolidation in other situations where someone has strategic control over a global bottleneck for niche materials.

As another example, direct military spending on local domestic businesses that are fully subsidized to manufacture weapons in Canada will create new activities for other businesses in Canada. The government can create a vertically integrated business structure to produce new armaments in Canada, generating substantial sales of specialized products and employment opportunities. This requires a concept of political support that is beyond the scope of this article.

It may also be possible for Canadian military spending to be counted toward programs with global organizations, such as the IMF Poverty Reduction and Growth Trust. For example, Canada could make an in-kind contribution where the military builds infrastructure for a country that the IMF would pay for. Rather than cash, the Canadian military could provide specialized contractor services to build infrastructure for countries that are participating in these IMF programs.

Another opportunity for the military to spend on infrastructure is in Ukraine. There is a new model in which the Canadian military undertakes all stages of infrastructure repair and reconstruction within Ukraine on an international aid basis. For example, the Canadian military could manufacture the steel used to rebuild bridges and buildings. For another example, it could produce specialized types of concretes with additives that improve the strength of the concrete.

The Canadian federal budget can be creative in how it allocates funding, although the execution remains to be tested.

The military, broadly defined, may also incur spending on infrastructure in Canada. This type of spending could have many types. For example, improved public roads to remote locations in Canada with new support facilities could improve national security. For another example, the military could build ports in remote locations and allow commercial transport of mineral ores and other products, with handling capabilities. There may be opportunities for new transport hubs to be operated by the Canadian military that unlock new globally-significant economic opportunities with relatively small spending by Canada on domestic infrastructure.

Does military contracting have a multiplier effect on GDP across different countries over time? It is possible to explore the historical context of military spending and domestic GDP impacts for several case studies, such as the USA.

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